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Citizenship Education Across Policy and Practice Frameworks: Cross-Country Analysis of Italy and Belgium

Work package 3– Deliverable 3.2

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1. Executive summary

This report presents a cross-country analysis of citizenship education frameworks, focusing on how educational structures related to civic knowledge, civic identity, democratic participation, digital citizenship, and social inclusion are expressed at the policy level. The analysis is based on a corpus of official policy documents retrieved from the Eurydice database and national legislation archives, curriculum guidelines, among others, in Italy, with a comparative examination of citizenship education across the language communities of Belgium. In Italy, the analysis focuses on the legal and regulatory framework of Educazione civica (Civic Education), i.e., Law No. 92/2019 and subsequent amendments thereto, Ministerial Decrees, Curriculum Guidelines, Anti-Bullying Legislation and related national frameworks. In Belgium, the analysis looks into the aspects of civic education across the different linguistic communities in each country. Both internal (intranational; within Belgium) and external (international; Italy/Belgium) comparisons were conducted.

2. About DEMINE

Demine Goals

Globalisation and immigration have altered intercommunity relations, leading to a rise in intergroup conflict marked by discrimination against diverse minorities. This has given way to various forms of radicalisation and extremism, spanning religious, political, and xenophobic spectrums worldwide. Globalisation and immigration strain social cohesion (shared public values, group norms, guiding principles) in numerous countries. While individual attitudes may not have shifted significantly, the prominence of migration in public discourse and the polarisation of public opinion have increased substantially. As a result, a divided public opinion has become more overtly hostile towards migration.

The DEMINE (DEaling with conflicts related to MIgration: NEgotiating social cohesion through communication) European Joint Doctorate (DN-JD) network is a collaborative effort across disciplines. Its primary goal is to enhance Europe's capacity to address a significant challenge: the rise of various forms of radicalisation and extremism that pose a threat to social cohesion. Through a combination of inter-sectoral mobility and a balanced blend of research and transferable competences, DEMINE develops a much-needed framework on the role and interplay of interpersonal and mediated communication in intergroup relations and conflict related to migration and globalisation, ultimately contributing to social cohesion. DEMINE has crafted a comprehensive research and training programme to examine the complex relationships between various forms of communication, including traditional media, social media, and interpersonal interactions. This programme aims to understand how various communication channels shape individual attitudes and beliefs regarding migration, as well as their impact on intergroup dynamics (social cohesion), especially within the broader context of political and societal polarisation, and the processes of radicalisation, with a specific focus on migration-related aspects.

DEMINE Educational Goals

- Train nine doctoral candidates to become the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers skilled in digital methods, participatory community research, and the evaluation of intergroup conflicts.
- Equip candidates with advanced theoretical and practical knowledge, focusing on strategic analysis, community-based participatory youth work, and open-source intelligence techniques.
- Develop transferable skills such as self-management, inter-sectoral collaboration, and innovation-oriented thinking to prepare candidates for both academic and non-academic careers.
- Promote interdisciplinary and international mobility, enabling candidates to apply their research findings in real-world contexts and contribute to professional fields ranging from strategic analysis to media production.

DEMINE Research Goals

- Identify and analyze the differences and similarities across various forms of socially unacceptable, extreme discourse, particularly related to migration, at the intersections of politics, media, and interpersonal communication.
- Investigate the impact of extreme discourse on individual attitudes and beliefs, with a specific focus on adolescents and vulnerable populations, while understanding the socio-demographic and psychological factors influencing susceptibility.

- Develop countermeasures to empower adolescents, news media producers, and political actors to mitigate the societal impact of divisive discourse, fostering social cohesion and reinforcing democratic principles.
- Provide a nuanced, cross-cultural, and interdisciplinary understanding of the mechanisms of polarization and radicalization to inform effective strategies and policy interventions.

By integrating these educational and research goals, DEMINE aims to enhance Europe's capacity to address the growing societal challenges linked to migration, fostering resilience and inclusivity in an increasingly polarized world.

DEMINE Consortium

DEMINE consists of three academic partners namely, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Aarhus Universitet, and Università Degli Studi di Padova as well as nine non-academic partners including OCAM-OCAD, City of Mechelen, Textgain, The Migration Policy Group, Refugees Welcome, Institut for Menneskerettigheder, Stichting Bellingcat, Verwey-Jonker Institute, and Hannah Arendt Institute.

The DEMINE consortium will train nine doctoral candidates (DCs) within a cross-disciplinary and international environment, giving them the opportunity to network, study and collect data in Western, Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe (see secondments) in collaboration with academic and non-academic experts, with ample opportunities to develop transferable skills such as technology literacy, adaptability (i.e., not feeling helpless in the face of change), strong communication skills, and ability to work in a team, in a dependable and well-organised fashion.

3. Introduction

In an era marked by rapid and unprecedented global change, Citizenship Education (CE) has emerged as a strategic imperative for Western democracies. Over the past three decades, it has become a central priority within the European Union (EU)'s educational agenda and is commonly cited as a response to the challenges facing modern society and democracy today, including the climate crisis, eroding trust in democratic institutions, and the rise of populist ideologies (Isac et al., 2024; Joris et al., 2022). At the EU level, there are educational standards for the subject of CE that focus on developing young people into "cooperative individuals" who can become responsible and informed citizens across all societal levels (Bacian & Huemer, 2023). However, this surge in attention is often accompanied by an "historically untested symbolic equivalence," where it is assumed that more formal schooling automatically expands civic capacity without explicitly defining the underlying relationship between education and citizenship (Joris et al., 2022).

This report sheds light on a critical gap by examining how CE is structured and implemented in two different institutional settings, i.e., Italy and Belgium. The Italian context has a framework established via the transversal, compulsory mandate of Law No. 92/2019. In contrast, the Belgian context is characterized as highly decentralized, where CE is anchored in constitutional values of neutrality but varies significantly across language communities. The analysis is guided by three research questions: (1) How does CE appear in the selected Italian and Belgian policy and curriculum documents? (2) Which civic, social, digital, and pedagogical elements are emphasized/prioritized in these frameworks? (3) What similarities and differences emerge across the Italian and Belgian cases? A total of 37 official policy documents are analyzed to identify broader trends within the civic, social, and digital dimensions of CE and establish the many ways through which educational institutions pursue their goals, be they legal, curricular, or through cross-curricular methods (Eurydice, 2017).

4. Methodology

This report examines how CE is defined, structured and operationalized through policies and curricula in Italy and Belgium. It looks at both national and subnational variation (in the case of the Belgian language communities) to document different ways that CE can be framed within an institution.

4.1 Analytical Approach

The study drawn for this report adopts a qualitative document analysis design. Rather than mere data sources for policy and curricula, documents are treated as texts which represent policy statements for institutional priorities, normative assumptions, and methods of implementing desired outcomes (Bowen, 2009; Dalglish et al., 2020; Morgan, 2022). The analytical strategy adopted is qualitative content analysis and thematic analysis; the former combines systematic coding with interpretive attention to broader patterns of meaning across the corpus (Braun & Clarke, 2021; Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2019; Schreier, 2012).

The coding process followed an inductive-deductive approach. Themes were initially identified from the documents themselves, they emerged inductively from the empirical data. Subsequently, these themes were organized into broader analytical categories based upon the research objectives and related literature addressing CE, student participation, inclusion, and digital literacy. As a result, the coding process was also deductive. More broadly, the analysis developed abductively throughout iterative cycles between the empirical materials, the conceptual framework guiding the analysis, and the analytical categories. This allowed the study to remain empirically grounded in the documents while simultaneously ensuring that the coding structure aligned with the primary aims (Fereday & Muir-Cochrane, 2006; Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2019).

4.2 Corpus and Coding Procedure

Corpus.

The analysis was conducted on a corpus of official policy and curriculum documents from Italy and Belgium. The Italian corpus consisted of 18 national-level documents, while the Belgian corpus comprised 19 such documents. Included within this corpus were laws, ministerial decrees, curricular frameworks, policy strategies, and supranational reference documents. All documents analyzed were retrieved from official institutional repositories, including ministerial websites, parliamentary or governmental databases, official government publications/gazettes, and, where relevant, EU documentation portals. A detailed listing of all texts used in this report is presented in *Appendices (under Table 1)*.

Data extraction.

Data extraction was the first phase of the analysis with the aim of transforming each document into the structured format of a spreadsheet. For each text, therefore, the extraction sheet recorded

bibliographic information, document type, policy level, issuing body, year, relevant themes, a short analytical summary, key quotations, and interpretive notes. This stage also served as the first step toward a familiarization with the whole corpus and allowed for the identification of recurrent themes among the selected documents.

Theme standardisation.

In the first stage of data extraction, most of the identified themes coincided with the original text wording itself and included terms such as *Constitution*, *Rights-Duties*, *Digital Citizenship*, *Media Literacy*, *Sustainability*, *Participation*, *Financial Education*, *School-Community Links*, etc., Given that these first-cycle themes were numerous and uneven in terms of scope and for systematic comparative analyses, a second stage followed aimed at their standardization and aggregation. At this stage, similar or overlapping themes were aggregated using standardized labels added to the “standardized theme” column of the extraction sheet. This process reduced redundancy and ensured similar concepts were treated consistently across the corpus.

Codebook construction.

The resulting codebook was developed as a result of an iterative process between the empirical materials and the study's conceptual framework. Categories were derived from recurring policy content within the documents themselves, whereas definitions for categories were informed by related literature and by the analytical purposes for answering the research questions. Thus, examples provided for illustrating categories are based on the corpus and boundaries for categories were theoretically defined. A total of 8 categories formed part of the final coding framework: *Civic-Constitutional Knowledge*; *Civic Participation & Engagement*; *Social Inclusion/Equality/Well-being*; *Digital Citizenship/Critical Digital Literacy*; *Data/Algorithms/Tech Awareness*; *Sustainability/Economy/Future-Oriented Citizenship*; *Curriculum/Pedagogy/School Governance*; *Creativity/Culture/Expression*. Table 2 presents the analytical codebook applied to both the Italian and Belgian corpora.

Table2. Analytical codebook for the Italian and Belgian policy corpora

Code	Description	Examples from the corpus
Civic-constitutional knowledge	This code is grounded in the dimension of "qualification," focusing on the transmission of knowledge regarding the State and its institutions to ensure students understand the functional mechanisms of democracy (Joris et al., 2022). Academic mapping identifies this as a fundamental pillar centered on "civic-constitutional knowledge" (Bozkurt et al., 2021).	Italy: Law 92/2019 establishes that "knowledge of the Italian Constitution" is the foundation of Civic Education, requiring students to study the "organisation of the State and of regional and local authorities" and "symbols of the Italian and EU institutions".
Civic participation and engagement	Literature views this as "socialization" or empowerment leading to active engagement in the political and civil spheres (Joris et al., 2022). It often refers to the Westheimer and Kahne (2004) typology, which distinguishes between personally responsible, participatory, and justice-oriented citizens (Bozkurt et al., 2021).	Italy: Implementation includes "Transversal Competence and Guidance Pathways (PCTO)," which require students to spend up to 210 hours (in vocational tracks) blending classroom instruction with host organization experience to foster active citizenship.
Social inclusion, equality, and wellbeing	This relates to the "social dimension" of citizenship, resonating with Marshall's (1950) concept that modern democracy requires social rights to counteract inequality (Vandevelde et al., 2025). It focuses on promoting social justice, human rights, and the protection of dignity (Jerome et al., 2024).	Italy: National laws focus on the "prevention and contrast of bullying and cyberbullying" to protect the psychophysical well-being and social inclusion of minors.
Digital citizenship and critical digital literacy	Policy framing is often restricted to individual "responsible behavior" and risk awareness rather than a structural political lens (Isac et al., 2024; Tahirsylaj & Sundberg, 2026). It involves the ability to "use virtual communication tools consciously and responsibly"	Italy: Article 5 of Law 92/2019 defines digital citizenship as the ability to "analyze, compare and critically assess the credibility" of digital sources. The 2024 guidelines notably include a "ban of smartphones from pre-primary to lower secondary education".

Code	Description	Examples from the corpus
Data, algorithms, and technological awareness	This category addresses the "black box" of modern technology, including how data is structured and how algorithms and AI function (EPRS, 2024). It is defined by "digital Bildung," which incorporates a holistic understanding of risks and opportunities in a digitalized society (Tahirsylaj & Sundberg, 2026).	Italy: The "Sillabo per l'Educazione Civica Digitale" (2018) provides a framework for "algorithmic awareness," specifically discussing the implications of "filter bubbles" and "big data" for democracy.
Sustainability, economy, and future-oriented citizenship	Grounded in the UN 2030 Agenda, this category links citizenship to "global developments and sustainability" (European Commission, 2024). It encourages understanding the interdependence of natural, socio-economic, and political systems	Italy: One of the three interdisciplinary pillars is "Sustainable Development," which covers environmental protection, health education, and "valuing work and entrepreneurship".
Curriculum, pedagogy, and school governance	Focuses on the shift toward student-centered "cross-curricula" based on complementary learning outcomes (Tahirsylaj & Sundberg, 2026). It emphasizes "whole-school approaches" embedded in development plans and school leadership.	Italy: Civic education is a compulsory transversal subject requiring at least 33 hours per year, integrated into all subjects without increasing total teaching hours.
Creativity, culture, and expression	Relates to "cultural awareness and expression," identifying it as a key competence for personal fulfillment and active citizenship. It involves understanding the "stratification of identities" (Joris et al., 2022).	Creativity, culture, and expression

Coding application.

Post the codebook construction, each document was reread and coded based on the eight categories. Each document contained a series of numerical codes (1 = category is mentioned/ present; 0 = category is not mentioned/ absent) that were used to create an analytical coding matrix. The creation of such a matrix helped shift from analyzing individual documents' thematic content to comparing the various dimensions of the data. The coding process also drew on summary information, quotes and

other interpretation-related material to evaluate the importance of each theme to the respective texts, as well as what role they played functionally in those texts.

Comparative analysis.

In order to identify common trends throughout the corpus, comparative tables and visual representations were used to organize the coded data. For both corpora, Italy and Belgium, the organization included frequency tables, document-type summaries, and a visual representation of the distribution of analytical dimensions.

The last step involved a cross-case analysis. Applying the same coding framework that had been applied to both data sets helped identify convergences and divergences in the conceptualisation and operationalisation of CE across the Italian and Belgian cases. A comparative matrix was developed to visualize all the categories distributed among the two data sets and to systematically compare them. Matrix-based displays are widely used as a tool for qualitative research as they provide a high level of analytic transparency while also enable researchers to visually assess commonality among documents (Miles et al., 2020) and in this study, the matrix formed the foundation for comparing the relative emphasis given to each of the five aspects of CE (constitutional knowledge, participatory citizenship, social inclusion, digital-critical dimensions, and institutional implementation) across the two settings.

5. Results

5.1 The Italian National Policy Corpus on Citizenship Education

The Italian corpus encompasses 18 documents: pivoting CE policy and framework as well as digital education, anti-bullying policies, curriculum development and constitutional foundations. Table 3 lists the type of documents used in this context; the majority are either legislation (n=4; 22.2%) or ministerial decrees (n=4; 22.2%); there are also three documents classified as guidelines (n=3; 16.7%) and two documents representing EU recommendations (n=2; 11.1%). All of the remaining documents represent an amendment to a law (n=1), a legislative decree (n=1), a document providing curriculum advice (n=1), a constitutional text (n=1) and a document outlining an educational policy strategy (n=1). The composition of this collection shows how CE in Italy has not been regulated using a single policy instrument, yet it is governed by a multi-layered structure of binding legislation, ministerial implementation measures, curricular orientation and supra-national references (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2017).

Table 3. Document types in the Italian corpus (N = 18)

Document type	n	%
Law	4	22.2
Ministerial Decree	4	22.2
Guidelines	3	16.7
EU Recommendation	2	11.1
Law (Amending law)	1	5.6
Legislative Decree	1	5.6
Curriculum Guidelines	1	5.6
Constitution (Foundational Legal Framework)	1	5.6
Education policy strategy	1	5.6

The most commonly referenced analytical theme across the entire corpus is curriculum, pedagogy and school governance. This theme was mentioned within 16 out of 18 documents (88.9%); a high prevalence that reflects the institutionalization of CE following Law 92/2019, which has established it as a mandatory, transversal subject requiring at least 33 hours of instruction per year (Eurydice Unit Italy, 2024). As such, the Italian policy approach views CE not solely as a collection of civic knowledge/competence, but it is an area for developing curricula, designing pedagogy, assessing student learning, planning schools and determining the logical foundations of schooling (Losito, 2022; Isac et al., 2024).

The second most frequently referenced theme is social inclusion, equity and well-being, which was identified in 15 documents (83.3%). A finding that highlights a prioritization of the "socialization" function of education and hence aims to involve young people in existing social and political orders through values of solidarity, dignity, and anti-violence (Isac et al., 2024; Vandeveldel et al., 2025). This framing aligns with what T.H. Marshall (1950) argues, full democratic citizenship requires social rights to counteract inequality; and hence, schools in Italy may be leveraged to provide a "compensatory effect" by offering civic experiences that students may not receive at home (Jerome et al., 2024).

Following close behind, digital citizenship/critical digital literacy was found in 14 documents (77.8%). In fact, a critical tension is evident in the results for the latter trend compared to data, algorithms, and technological awareness (11.1%) and the four documents (22.2%) that discussed issues relating to creativity, culture and self-expression. In Italy, digital citizenship is explicitly codified as one of the three main pillars of CE, yet it is framed primarily in terms of "responsible practices" and risk awareness, such as the ban on smartphones in lower secondary education (Isac et al., 2024). This near-absence of topics related to datafication and algorithms suggests that the policy framework addresses technology as a behavioral issue rather than a structural one, leaving the "black box" of deep technological infrastructures and algorithmic mediation largely unaddressed (UNESCO, 2023).

Meanwhile, sustainable economies/future-oriented citizenship, which was represented in 13 documents (72.2%), is a core pillar aligned with the UN 2030 Agenda; its implementation faces a significant "knowledge-action gap"(European Commission, 2024).

Table 4. Frequency of analytical themes across the corpus (N = 18)

Analytical themes	Documents coded	% of corpus
Curriculum, pedagogy, and school governance	16	88.9
Social inclusion, equality, and wellbeing	15	83.3
Digital citizenship and critical digital literacy	14	77.8
Sustainability, economy, and future-oriented citizenship	13	72.2
Civic-constitutional knowledge	11	61.1
Civic participation and engagement	11	61.1
Creativity, culture, and expression	4	22.2
Data, algorithms, and technological awareness	2	11.1

Table 4 presents the frequency of the analytical dimensions across the Italian corpus and facilitates comparison across categories, while Figure 1 visualises the same distribution.

Fig. 1 Distribution of analytical dimensions across the Italian policy corpus

These trends shed light on how the Italian government has prioritised the institutionalisation of CE through the development of pedagogy and social cohesion, while they also indicate how this former has given much less attention to the development of systemic infrastructure that shapes digital life. Digital citizenship education has evolved toward safe usage but has not yet reached the structural political dimensions of artificial intelligence and mediated decision-making processes necessary for a dynamic democracy (Greco et al., 2023).

5.1.2 Italian Policy Instruments and The Structuring of Citizenship Education

To understand how CE trends occur across the policy instruments, Table 5 compares a selected set of analytical codes/ themes across various document categories. Laws (4/4) have a particular emphasis on digital citizenship, critical digital literacy, as well as on social inclusion, equality, and wellbeing; this latter goes hand in hand with the legal foundation of CE as a mandatory, transversal mandate (Law 92/2019). Meanwhile, ministerial decrees (4/4) are particularly associated with curriculum, pedagogy, school governance, and civic-constitutional knowledge. Guidelines offered a more balanced coverage of civic, digital, and social dimensions and hence acted as the bridge between legal obligation and classroom practice. The EU recommendations (2/2) are the most even category, they represent broad "competence models" rather than specific instructional mandates. Consequently, while the EU provides the conceptual "toolkit" of knowledge, skills, and values, national authorities use laws and decrees to adapt these to specific cultural path-dependencies (Joris et al., 2022; Tahirsylaj & Sundberg, 2026). Yet, the high prevalence of digital themes in laws contrasted with the low visibility of data structures highlights how at the highest level of obligation, policy remains focused on individual "responsible behavior" and risk awareness rather than the structural political dimensions of the digital environment (Isac et al., 2024). This pattern supports the interpretation that CE functions as a "travelling policy" with each instrument having a role: EU frameworks serve as the normative foundation for building a shared European civic identity; laws establish scope and obligation, and decrees and guidelines provide operationalized curricula/pedagogies, (Isac et al., 2024; Joris et al., 2022; Tahirsylaj & Sundberg, 2026).

All in all, the Italian policy corpus constructs CE to be a wide-ranging educational area based on curricular governance, competence-based pedagogies, inclusion-oriented values, and an increasingly visible digital citizenship agenda. This feature situates it within the larger European/international trend toward multilevel and multidimensional CE (Joris, 2022). At the same time, the corpus reveals a critical gap: digital responsibility, media literacy, and critical source evaluation are better established throughout the entire corpus than are the structural dimensions of digital power (i.e., data systems, algorithms, and platform governance) which remain less developed.

Table 5. Selected code/theme presence by Policy document type

Themes	Civic-constitutional knowledge	Digital citizenship and critical digital literacy	Social inclusion, equality, and wellbeing	Sustainability, economy, and future-oriented citizenship	Curriculum, pedagogy, and school governance
Policy Document type					
Law (n = 4)	1	4	4	2	4
Ministerial Decree (n = 4)	3	2	1	3	4
Guidelines (n = 3)	2	3	3	2	3
EU Recommendation (n = 2)	2	2	2	2	2
Law (Amending law) (n = 1)	1	0	1	1	0
Legislative Decree (n = 1)	0	1	1	0	1
Curriculum Guidelines (n = 1)	1	1	1	1	1
Constitution (n = 1)	1	0	1	1	0
Education policy strategy (n = 1)	0	1	1	1	1

5.2 The Belgian National Policy Corpus on Citizenship Education

The Belgian corpus covers 19 documents focusing on the constitutional basis of education, citizenship and philosophy education, curriculum frameworks, participation structures, equal opportunity measures, and education policy. Table 6 lists the types of documents included in this corpus; the majority of these are community-level legislative decrees (n=9; 47.4%). There are also ministerial decrees (n=2; 10.5%) and curriculum guidelines (n=3; 15.8%). All of the remaining documents consist of a guideline (n=1; 5.3%), an EU recommendation/overview (n=1; 5.3%), a law amending law (n=1; 5.3%), a constitutional text (n=1; 5.3%), and an education policy strategy (n=1; 5.3%).

Table 6. Document types in the Belgian corpus (N = 19)

Document type	n	%
Law	0	0
Ministerial Decree	2	10.5
Guidelines	1	5.3
EU Recommendation	1	5.3
Law (Amending law)	1	5.3
Legislative Decree	9	47.4
Curriculum Guidelines	3	15.8
Constitution (Foundational Legal Framework)	1	5.3
Education policy strategy	1	5.3

The predominant analytical theme across the Belgian corpus is the organization of curriculum, pedagogy, and school governance, which appears in 89.5% (17 out of 19) of the documents. As such, the Belgian policy approach views CE as a collection of civic knowledge and competences organised through the schools curriculum, pedagogical approach, school participation structures, and community-level governance arrangements. This aspect is highlighted in the Flemish competence-based framework, which has transitioned from a tradition of "hesitation" regarding state intervention in normative issues toward the introduction of mandatory, results-based competence frameworks (Loobuyck, 2021); while the French Community focuses on philosophy and citizenship guidelines, and the German-speaking Community adopts a cross-curricular and interdisciplinary model. An approach that aligns with the broader European trend of competence-based education (CBE), where supranational visions are recontextualized into specific national instructional mandates (Tahirsylaj & Sundberg, 2026).

As presented in Table 7, the second most frequently referenced themes are civic-constitutional knowledge, civic participation and engagement, as well as social inclusion, equality, and wellbeing, each identified in 14 documents (73.7%). Similar to the Italian context, this latter sheds light on how CE in the Belgian Communities is primarily used for the "socialization" function of education (Joris et al., 2022), and hence they place strong emphasis on democratic principles, participatory practices, and inclusive educational values. In the French Community, this is institutionalized through the explicit subject "Philosophy and Citizenship" (Citoyenneté et Philosophie), while the Flemish Community employ participation decrees to grant students formal roles in school governance (Bacian & Huemer, 2023; Isac et al., 2024). On the other hand, the analysis also identifies a critical gap for digital citizenship (21.1%) and a total absence of topics on data, algorithms and technical awareness (0%). Although some marginal references to digital themes can be found in educational training materials, such as "algorithmic methods" and "fake news", this theme is totally absent in core educational

curricula. Likewise, the moderate level of presence of education on sustainable development (26.3%) highlights a potential "knowledge-action gap," where high levels of student environmental awareness do not necessarily translate into active civic agency (European Commission, 2024).

Table 7. Frequency of analytical codes across the corpus (N = 19)

Analytical code	Documents coded	% of corpus
Curriculum, pedagogy, and school governance	17	89.5
Social inclusion, equality, and wellbeing	14	73.7
Digital citizenship and critical digital literacy	4	21.1
Sustainability, economy, and future-oriented citizenship	5	26.3
Civic-constitutional knowledge	14	73.7
Civic participation and engagement	14	73.7
Creativity, culture, and expression	7	36.8
Data, algorithms, and technological awareness	0	0

Similar to the Italian context, the data in Table 7 show the frequency of the analytical categories taking place throughout the Italian corpus, while Figure 1 illustrates the same distribution of data.

Fig. 2 Distribution of analytical dimensions across the Belgian corpus

5.2.2 Belgian Policy Instruments and the Structuring of Citizenship Education

To understand how citizenship educational trends occur across the policy instruments, Table 8 indicates that the majority of the documents collected for Belgium were related to legislative decrees

(n=9), whereas three were classified under “curriculum guides” (n=3), two of ministerial decrees (n=2), and only single instances of other document types. Within these categories, social inclusion, equality, and well-being, curriculum, pedagogy, and school governance; along with civic-constitutional knowledge, are the strongest analytical dimensions among those listed in Table 8. Both social inclusion, equality, and well-being and curriculum, pedagogy, and school governance appeared 8 times, respectively, in legislative decrees, whereas civic-constitutional knowledge appeared 6 times in the same category. In contrast, Curriculum guidelines (n=3) also show consistent presence across civic-constitutional knowledge (3), social inclusion, equality, and well-being (3), and curriculum, pedagogy, and school governance (3). As a result, CE in the Belgian corpus is institutionalised mainly through legislative and curricular instruments and is embedded in the formal organisation of schooling rather than through a broad national legislative framework alone. At the same time, digital citizenship and critical digital literacy appear solely twice in legislative decrees, once in curriculum guides, and are absent in several other document types. Accordingly, while digital dimensions of CE exist within the data set, they are less systematically developed than constitutional, inclusion-related, and governance-oriented dimensions.

Table 8. Selected code presence by document type

Document type	Civic-constitutional knowledge	Digital citizenship and critical digital literacy	Social inclusion, equality, and wellbeing	Sustainability, economy, and future-oriented citizenship	Curriculum, pedagogy, and school governance
Law (n = 0)	0	0	0	0	0
Ministerial Decree (n = 2)	1	0	0	0	2
Guidelines (n = 1)	1	0	0	0	0
EU Recommendation (n = 1)	1	0	0	0	1
Law (Amending law) (n = 1)	1	1	1	1	1
Legislative Decree (n = 9)	6	2	8	2	8
Curriculum Guidelines (n = 3)	3	1	3	1	3
Constitution (n = 1)	1	0	1	0	1
Education policy	0	0	1	1	1

strategy (n = 1)					
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All in all, the Belgian policy constructs CE as an educational and governmental initiative to create civic-minded students who will participate in democracy and have knowledge about their civic responsibilities (Joris et al., 2022; Isac et al., 2024). This aligns with the IEA/ICCS interdisciplinary model that views citizenship as a "toolkit" of psychological resources, be it knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values, that students need to acquire to navigate the complexities of modern democratic society's social, economic, and political systems. Nonetheless, it reveals a total absence of structural digital awareness (Moons & Duchateau, 2024)

6. A Comparative Analysis of Policy Frameworks

The analysis of 37 Italian and Belgian policy documents shows a paradigmatic shift, mostly in how to deem CE as it transitions from isolated subjects to integrated systems of government and transversal-based schooling. This section synthesizes the findings in the wider context of current trends in European education.

The Primacy of Governance and Transversal Integration

The focus on Curriculum/Pedagogy/School Governance in 89.5% of the entire corpus reflects a new paradigm for European Educational Policy shift focused on “Seamless Enactment”, a model to produce harmony between educational ends and means by embedding democratic values into every step of the school's organizational structure (Joris et al., 2022). For instance, Law 92/2019 in Italy created a legally binding obligation for schools to introduce the CE as a compulsory subject throughout the whole school system with a minimum number of lessons (33 hours/year), and to be integrated within already existing subjects (Isac et al., 2024). On the other hand, in Belgium, there exists a decentralized framework for student involvement, but it is very much institutionalized. A case in point in Flanders, the Decree regarding Student Participation in School Organizations formally assigns roles to students in the decision-making process of their schools. Likewise, the French Community has introduced the subject “Citizenship and Philosophy” (Citoyenneté et Philosophie) specifically designed for CE purposes (Bacian & Huemer, 2023).

Socialization vs. Subjectification: The Competence Model Critique

High levels of social inclusion, equality, and well-being were seen across both countries, with 83.3% in Italy and 73.7%, indicating that both countries prioritize the role of "socialization," which introduces youth to existing social and political orders (Joris et al., 2022). Within Italian schools, this has been

framed as promoting legality, solidarity, and anti-bullying measures, while also framing citizenship as a tool of social cohesion (Eurydice, 2024). While this focus is a *sine qua non*, the “citizenship-as-competence” model is dominant in European policy; this model portrays citizenship as an individual toolkit of knowledge and skills (Joris et al., 2022), thus potentially depoliticizing education. Critics argue that by focusing on personal “learning outcomes,” policies may inadvertently shift the responsibility for social issues onto individual students, and hence neglecting “subjectification” or emancipation, i.e., the development of an autonomous, critical voice— necessary for citizens to question and change existing power structures (Joris et al., 2022).

Critical Gaps in Digital and Sustainability Literacies

A significant divergence appears in the area of digital citizenship. While it occurs in nearly 80% of all Italian documents, the framing is overall restricted to “responsible practices” and risk awareness, e.g. the September 2024 guidelines banning smartphones in lower secondary education (Isac et al., 2024). The vast majority of these approaches do little to consider the underlying technologies of today's world; namely, how data is structured, how algorithms function, and how artificial intelligence is used. These were found to occur in less than 12% of all Italian examples and in less than one per cent of the larger study sample. A similar pattern of structural omission and behavioral framing is evident in the Belgian policy landscape, though digital citizenship appears far less frequently, featuring in only 21.1% of its official documents. Much like the Italian context, Belgian policy framing is restricted to individual “responsible behavior” and media literacy, leading to a near-total absence (0%) of content related to platform governance, algorithms, or AI within the core curriculum. The technological “black box” shaping so much of modern public life has moved beyond the scope of national educational policy; and as a result, many students will likely not develop the skills necessary to understand and mitigate the effects of both algorithmic bias and automation (EPRS, 2024), leading to a continued knowledge-action gap.

The Systemic “Blind Spot”: Technical and Vocational Education (TVET)

There is a major implementation barrier in technical and vocational education (TVET) or, as mentioned in the results, a systemic “blind spot” in both Italy and Belgium (Moons & Duchateau, 2024). Students pursuing technical and vocational training represent roughly 21% to 29% of the total student body; however, their performance on traditional knowledge-based civic assessments is significantly lower than that of students not enrolled in technical and vocational programs (Sampermans, et.al., 2021). A difference in scores can be linked to educational policy developed under assumptions of a normative “average” student using a didactic model that starts with theory, a method that teachers report being largely ineffective for vocational learners who thrive on hands-on models, “doing and experiencing”

(Moons & Duchateau, 2024). To embrace social cohesion, future frameworks must move beyond legalistic definitions and adopt experiential, community-based pedagogies.

7. Conclusion

The cross-country analysis of 37 policy documents shows how both Italy and Belgium have convergent goals with respect to democratic foundations; however, they each have different ways to develop active citizenship through institutions. One key finding is the emphasis placed on governance and transversal integration; both contexts demonstrate a strong commitment to promoting social inclusion, equality, and well-being. However, there are also significant gaps in terms of future-oriented literacies. Digital citizenship is a priority in Italy, but the framing of this policy is still centered around promoting "responsible behavior" and raising awareness of potential risks associated with technology use; for instance, banning smartphones rather than teaching the critical literacy skills needed to understand deeper technologies such as algorithms and artificial intelligence (Isac et al. 2024; EPRS 2024). There is also an identified knowledge-action gap regarding sustainability education (European Commission, 2024) and a systematic "blind spot" for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) where current Policy frameworks rely on "knowledge first" didactic models, which do not meet the needs of vocational learners (Moons & Duchateau 2024). As a result, to be fairly inclusive, CE should adopt experiential, neighborhood-oriented pedagogies that start with "doing and experiencing" (Moons & Duchateau, 2024); and to remain relevant in today's increasingly complex digital environment and geopolitics, it must move away from traditional or static representations of what citizenship means and hence employ a "whole school approach", one that empowers students to act as agents of change in society (European Commission, 2024). Ultimately, the goal of CE is the cultivation of skills, values, and attitudes necessary for a resilient democracy.

8. Reference

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Table 1. Policy and curriculum documents: Italy & Belgium

Country	Document Title	Type	Level	Issuing Body	Year	URL or Source
Italy	Legge 20 Agosto 2019, N. 92 - Introduzione Dell'insegnamento Scolastico Dell'educazione Civica (19g00105)	Law	National	Italian Parliament	2019	https://www.normattiva.it/esprta/attoCompleto?atto.dataPubblicazioneGazzetta=2019-08-21&atto.codiceRedazionale=19G00105 https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/atto/stampa/serie_generale/originario
Italy	Legge 17 Febbraio 2025, N. 21 – Modifica All'articolo 3 Della Legge 20 Agosto 2019, N. 92 Concernente L'introduzione Delle Conoscenze Di Base In Materia Di Sicurezza Nei Luoghi Di Lavoro Nell'ambito Di Insegnamento Dell'educazione Civica. (25g00021)	Law (Amending Law)	National	Italian Parliament	2025	LEGGE 17 febbraio 2025, n. 21
Italy	Decreto Ministeriale N. 1 – Istituzione Del Comitato Tecnico Scientifico Per Le Linee Guida Di Educazione Civica	Ministerial Decree	National	Ministry Of Education (Mim - Ministero Dell'istruzione E Del Merito)	2020	https://www.istruzione.it/educazione_civica/norme.html
Italy	Decreto Ministeriale N. 35 – Linee Guida Per L'insegnamento Dell'educazione Civica	Ministerial Decree	National	Ministry Of Education (Mim - Ministero Dell'istruzione E Del Merito)	2022	Decreto Ministeriale n.35 del 22 giugno 2020 - MIM
Italy	Allegati A, B, C Del Decreto Ministeriale N. 35 – Linee Guida Per L'insegnamento Dell'educazione Civica	Guidelines	National	Ministry Of Education (Mim - Ministero Dell'istruzione E Del Merito)	2022	Decreto Ministeriale n.35 del 22 giugno 2020 - MIM

Country	Document Title	Type	Level	Issuing Body	Year	URL or Source
Italy	Decreto Ministeriale N. 9 – Collaborazioni Scuola-Territorio Per Esperienze Extrascolastiche Di Educazione Civica	Ministerial Decree	National	Ministry Of Education (Mim - Ministero Dell'istruzione E Del Merito)	2021	Decreto ministeriale n. 9 del 7 gennaio 2021 - MIM
Italy	Decreto Ministeriale N. 183 – Adozione Delle Linee Guida Per L'insegnamento Dell'educazione Civica	Ministerial Decree	National	Ministry Of Education (Mim - Ministero Dell'istruzione E Del Merito)	2024	Atti e norme
Italy	Linee Guida Per L'insegnamento Dell'educazione Civica	Guidelines	National	Ministry Of Education (Mim - Ministero Dell'istruzione E Del Merito)	2024	Atti e norme
Italy	Raccomandazione (2006/962/Ce) Relativa A Competenze Chiave Per L'apprendimento Permanente	Eu Recommendation	European	European Parliament And Council Of The European Union	2006	32006H0962 - EN - EUR-Lex
Italy	Raccomandazione Relativa Alle Competenze Chiave Per L'apprendimento Permanente (2018/C 189/01)	Eu Recommendation	European	European Parliament And Council Of The European Union	2018	32018H0604(01) - EN - EUR-Lex
Italy	Legge 29 Maggio 2017, N. 7 – Disposizioni A Tutela Dei Minori Per La Prevenzione E Il Contrasto Del Fenomeno Del Cyberbullismo	Law	National	Italian Parliament	2017	Disposizioni a tutela dei minori per la prevenzione ed il contrasto del fenomeno del cyberbullismo
Italy	Legge 17 Maggio 2024, N. 70 – Disposizioni E Delega Al Governo In Materia Di Prevenzione E Contrasto Del Bullismo E Del Cyberbullismo	Law	National	Italian Parliament	2024	https://www.normattiva.it/esperta/attoCompleto?atto.dataPubblicazioneGazzetta=2017-06-03&atto.codiceRedazionale=17G00085
Italy	Decreto Legislativo 12 Giugno 2025, N. 99– Disposizioni In Materia Di Prevenzione E Contrasto Del Bullismo E Del Cyberbullismo	Legislative Decree	National	Republic Of Italy / Government (Legislative Decree Issued Under Parliamentary Delegation - Law 70/2024)	2025	DECRETO LEGISLATIVO 12 giugno 2025, n. 99

Country	Document Title	Type	Level	Issuing Body	Year	URL or Source
Italy	Indicazioni Nazionali Per Il Curricolo –Scuola Dell’infanzia E Scuole Del Primo Ciclo Di Istruzione	Curriculum Guidelines	National	Ministry Of Education (Mim - Ministero Dell’istruzione E Del Merito)	2025	Nuove Indicazioni nazionali: concluso iter competenza del Ministero - MIM
Italy	Costituzione Italiana	Constitution (Foundational Legal Framework)	National	Constituent Assembly Of The Italian Republic	1948	La Costituzione Senato della Repubblica
Italy	Legge 13 Luglio 2015, N. 107 – “La Buona Scuola”	Law	National	Italian Parliament	2015	https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2015-07-13;107!vig=
Italy	Piano Nazionale Scuola Digitale - Pnsd	Education Policy Strategy	National	Ministry Of Education (Mim - Ministero Dell’istruzione E Del Merito)	2007	https://www.mim.gov.it/scuola-digitale
Italy	Sillabo Sull’educazione Civica Digitale	Guidelines	National	Ministry Of Education (Mim - Ministero Dell’istruzione E Del Merito)	2018	https://scuoladigitale.istruzione.it/iniziativa-competenz/sillabo-sulleducazione-civica-digitale/
Belgium	Constitution Of Belgium, Article 24	Constitutional Provision	National	Belgian Federal State	1831	https://www.senate.be/doc/const_fr.html
Belgium	Overview- Belgium: Flemish Community	European Commission Overview	European	Eurydice Vlaanderen / Department Of Education And Training	Revised: 2024	https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/eurypedia/belgium-flemish-community/overview
Belgium	Codex Secundair Onderwijs	Code / Codified Legal Framework	Flemish Community	Flemish Parliament	2010	https://codex.vlaanderen.be/Zoeken/Document.aspx?DID=1020342&param=inhoud&ref=search&AVIDS=
Belgium	Uitgangspunten	Policy Guide	Flemish Education Authorities / Onderwijsdoelen	Flemish Government	Accessed 16 March 2026)	https://onderwijsdoelen.be/uitgangspunten/4825
Belgium	Decreet Betreffende Participatie Op School En De Vlaamse Onderwijsraad	Decree / Legal Text	Flemish Community	Flemish Parliament	2004	https://codex.vlaanderen.be/Portals/Codex/documenten/1013317.html

Country	Document Title	Type	Level	Issuing Body	Year	URL or Source
Belgium	Décret Définissant Les Missions Prioritaires De L'enseignement Fondamental Et De L'enseignement Secondaire	Decree / Legal Text	French Community	Parlement De La Communauté Française	1997	https://gallilex.cfwb.be/#::~:text=Votre%20acc%C3%A8s%20au%20droit%20de,%C3%A0%20disposition%20la%20%C3%A9gislation%20consolid%C3%A9e.
Belgium	Décret Relatif Au Renforcement De L'éducation À La Citoyenneté	Decree / Legal Text	French Community	Parlement De La Communauté Française	2007	https://gallilex.cfwb.be/#::~:text=Votre%20acc%C3%A8s%20au%20droit%20de,%C3%A0%20disposition%20la%20%C3%A9gislation%20consolid%C3%A9e.
Belgium	Code De L'enseignement Fondamental Et De L'enseignement Secondaire	Code / Codified Legal Framework	French Community	Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles	2019	https://gallilex.cfwb.be/textes-normatifs/49466
Belgium	Iccs 2016 Technical Report (Belgium - Flemish)	Report	International	International Association For The Evaluation Of Educational Achievement (Iea)	2016	https://www.iea.nl/sites/default/files/2019-07/ICCS%202016_Technical%20Report_FINAL.pdf
Belgium	Rahmenplan Für Die Primarschule Und Die Regel Sekundarschule	Official Curriculum Framework	German-Speaking Community	Ministerium Der Deutschsprachigen Gemeinschaft Belgiens	2016	https://ostbelgienbildung.be/PortalData/21/Resources/downloads/schule_ausbildung/schulische_ausbildung/rahmenplaene_neu/RP_Ethik_PRIM_SEK.pdf
Belgium	Rahmenplan Orientierter Leitfaden Für Die Politisch-Demokratische Bildung	Policy Guide	German-Speaking Community	Ministerium Der Deutschsprachigen Gemeinschaft Belgiens	2019	https://ostbelgienbildung.be/PortalData/21/Resources/downloads/schule_ausbildung/schulische_ausbildung/politische_bildung/190705_Anhang_1_LeitfadenPB_Deutschsprachige_Gemeinschaft.pdf?utm_
Belgium	Décret Relatif À L'organisation D'un Cours Et D'une Éducation À La Philosophie Et À La Citoyenneté	Decree / Legal Text	French Community	Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles	2015	https://gallilex.cfwb.be/sites/default/files/imports/41979_000.pdf
Belgium	Decreet Basisonderwijs	Decree / Legal Text	Flemish Community	Flemish Government	2022	https://codex.vlaanderen.be/PrintDocument.ashx?datum=2022-09-01&geannoteerd=false&id=1005384&print=false&utm_

Country	Document Title	Type	Level	Issuing Body	Year	URL or Source
Belgium	Decreet Houdende Wijziging Van Het Decreet Basisonderwijs Van 25 Februari 1997	Decree / Legal Text	Flemish Community	Flemish Government	2018	https://codex.vlaanderen.be/PrintDocument.ashx?id=1029100&utm
Belgium	Décret Organisant Un Encadrement Différencié Au Sein Des Établissements Scolaires De La Communauté Française	Decree / Legal Text	French Community	Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles	2009	https://gallilex.cfwb.be/sites/default/files/imports/34295_024.pdf
Belgium	Decreet Over Het Jeugd- En Kinderrechtenbeleid En De Ondersteuning Van Het Jeugdwerk	Decree / Legal Text	Flemish Community	Flemish Government	2023	https://codex.opendata.api.vlaanderen.be/api/WetgevingDocument/1039169
Belgium	Arrêté Du Gouvernement De La Communauté Française	Decree / Legal Text	French Community	Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles	2025	https://gallilex.cfwb.be/sites/default/files/textes-normatifs/2025-04/53383_0000.pdf?utm_
Belgium	Gouvernements De Communaute Et De Region Gemeenschaps	Decree / Legal Text	French Community	Ministere De La Communaute Française	2025	https://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/mopdf/2025/02/10_1.pdf#page=58
Belgium	Bildungsvision 2040	Policy Guide	German-Speaking Community	Ministerium Der Deutschsprachigen Gemeinschaft Belgiens	2023	https://ostbelgienbildung.be/PortalData/21/Resources/downloads/allgemeine_infos/Bildungsvision_2040.pdf?utm_